

A Quantum Pulse Gate Enhanced Photonic Radar Architecture

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A novel radar architecture using a quantum pulse gate (QPG) for quantum uncertainty limited range resolution is introduced. Due to the inherent phase sensitivity of the process, the QPG enhanced radar architecture is able to overcome classical radar limits.

Radar based sensor systems provide many advantages compared to lidar or camera based sensor systems like e.g. radial velocity or range [1, 2]. A main drawback of state of the art pure electronic radar systems is the coarse angular resolution. The limiting factor are the high losses of electrical interconnects limiting the antenna aperture size [1, 2]. In contrast, fiber optical signalling provide relatively low losses, which make it attractive for radar. With a photonic radar system with fiber optical LO distribution arbitrary aperture sizes with arbitrary fine angular resolution can be realized.

Since the distance to the target is proportional to the round trip delay, time delay measurements are essential for radar systems. In [3] a time delay measurement scheme for ultimate quantum precision was presented. Therefore a QPG, which is a reconfigurable temporal mode demultiplexer, perform the necessary projective measurement. Fig. 1a shows the measurement results of the time offset [3]. The first distance measurement with a QPG, shown in fig. 1b, demonstrate the potential of the approach [4].

FIG. 1: (a) Estimation of the time offset [3]; (b) Measurement results of a QPG enhanced lidar system [4]; (c) Simplified block diagram of the QPG enhanced photonic radar.

The novel QPG enhanced photonic radar architecture is shown in fig. 1c. The output signal of the optical modulator, fed by a continuous wave laser, is distributed to the photonic radar transmitter (TX) frontend. In the TX frontend, the optical signal is converted to an electrical by means of a photodiode and a transimpedance amplifier. The weak electrical signal is further amplified by a power amplifier, before it is transmitted via a transmit antenna. The backscattered signal is received using a receive antenna. The weak received signal is amplified by means of a low noise amplifier before an optical signal is modulated. The optical signal of the received pulse is summed up with the optical transmit signal before both signals are fed to the QPG. In conjunction with the gating pulse, generated by a pulsed laser and a pulse shaper, the QPG perform the projections on both input signals to estimate the time difference.

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- [1] S. Kruse, S. Gudyriev, T. Schwabe, P. Kneuper, H. G. Kurz, and J. C. Scheytt, Silicon Photonic Radar Transmitter IC for mm-Wave Large Aperture MIMO Radar Using Optical Clock Distribution, *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters* **31**, 783 (2021).
 [2] S. Kruse, S. Gudyriev, P. Kneuper, T. Schwabe, M.-M. Meinecke, H. G. Kurz, and J. C. Scheytt, Silicon Photonic Radar Receiver IC for mm-Wave Large Aperture MIMO Radar Using Optical Clock Distribution, *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters* **32**, 1447 (2022).
 [3] V. Ansari, B. Brecht, J. Gil-Lopez, J. M. Donohue, J. Řeháček, Z. c. v. Hradil, L. L. Sánchez-Soto, and C. Silberhorn, Achieving the Ultimate Quantum Timing Resolution, *PRX Quantum* **2**, 010301 (2021).
 [4] S. Kruse, L. Serino, P. Folge, D. E. Oviedo, A. Bhattacharjee, M. Stefszky, J. C. Scheytt, B. Brecht, and C. Silberhorn, A Pulsed Lidar System With Ultimate Quantum Range Accuracy, *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters* **35**, 769 (2023).

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